

THE IMPORTANCE OF MACRONUTRIENTS IN THE CURRENT NUTRITION OF STUDENTS

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Abstract. *The article studies the current nutritional status of 1st-2nd-3rd year students of the Biology and Biotechnology department of Karshi State University during the winter season. When studying the current nutritional status of the students under observation, relevant differences were observed in the intake of proteins, fats, carbohydrates, and total calories of boys and girls in both age groups.*

Keywords: *healthy eating, healthy lifestyle, nutritionology, macronutrient, micronutrient.*

Introduction. Scientific research is being conducted on the fact that the increase in the number of various nutritional diseases in the world is due to the unhealthy diet of the population, and that a single violation of dietary norms can lead to a decrease in mental and physical performance, an increase or decrease in body weight, a decline in general intelligence, and a weakening of the body's ability to resist stress factors. In this regard, in recent years, this phenomenon has been observed not only among adults, but also among students, and in order to eliminate this in a timely manner, special attention is paid to the full organization of the daily diet and the constant implementation of propaganda work on healthy eating among the population [9,10]

Methodology. In recent years, special attention has been paid in our republic to widely promoting a healthy lifestyle among the population and one of its main principles, rational (healthy) nutrition. In this regard, efforts have been made to expand the main types of healthy and safe food raw materials, enrich food products with micronutrients, and develop recommended daily dietary intake standards for various population groups based on age, gender, physiological condition, and occupation.

Over the past 25-30 years, authoritative global organizations have begun to publish the results of nutrition monitoring of various population groups in local areas in order to protect human health and prevent non-communicable diseases [1,2,5,7,10].

The health of all segments of the population is formed during the period of growth and development under the influence of a complex of important internal factors and external influences. Along with environmental factors, a high-quality diet is also of great importance in the growth and all-round development of a person. Eating according to age, gender, work activity and health status has a positive effect not only on the growth and development of children and adolescents, but also on the working ability and health status of students [4].

In many studies conducted among students, it was noted that the order of food consumption in their daily diet, as well as the need for macro- and micronutrients, were not properly coordinated [3,4,9].

Research was conducted in the winter season of 2025 at the Faculty of Chemistry and Biology of Karshi State University. Students studying in the 1-2-3 stages of chemistry, biology and biotechnology were selected as respondents. They were 18-24 years old and totaled 145 people. 56 of them were boys and 89 were girls.

The amount of macronutrients in the daily food intake of students was studied in comparison with the existing physiological standards [6,8]. The current nutrition of students was studied in comparison with physiological requirements.

Results obtained and their analysis: The results of the study were compared with the norms of physiological requirements for nutrients and energy of various groups of the population of the Republic of Uzbekistan [8].

Tables 1-2 below provide information on the macronutrient supply of students in the winter season and the energy value of the main nutrients (proteins, fats, carbohydrates) in the foods consumed.

The proteins in the daily diet of boys from the study group amounted to 60.6 grams (15.8% less) instead of 72 grams.

In addition to their high energy value, fats, like proteins, are part of cells and tissues, acting as a building (plastic) material, and are important in the metabolism of proteins, vitamins, and minerals. The fat intake is 70.7 grams (12.7% less than the norm). Unlike proteins and fats, carbohydrate intake was 16.4% higher than the norm. The total energy content of macronutrients can be considered as around the norm (6.7% higher).

Table 1

Main nutrient intake of 18-24 year old boys during winter

№	Indicators (g)	The norm	Result	The difference
1	Proteins	72	60,6 ± 1,2	-15,8
2	Fats	81	70,7 ± 2,9	-12,7
3	Carbohydrates	358	417 ± 3,6	+16,4
4	Energy value Kcal	2450	2615,6	+6,7

The daily physiological protein intake of the 2nd group of subjects was 50.4 g (17.4% less) instead of the norm of 61 g. The total fat intake was 54 g (19.4% less) instead of 67 g. The total amount of carbohydrates in the daily diet of female students was 329.4 g instead of 289 g (13.9% more than the norm). The energy value of the main nutrients (proteins, fats, carbohydrates) in the food was accepted at the standard level, i.e. instead of 2000 kcal, 2059.4 kcal was consumed (2.9% more).

Table 2

Providing essential nutrients to girls aged 18-24 during the winter season

№	Indicators (g)	The norm	Result	The difference
1	Proteins	61	50,4 ± 1,0	-17,4
2	Fats	67	54 ± 3,2	-19,4
3	Carbohydrates	289	329,4 ± 4,6	+13,9
4	Energy value Kcal	2000	2059,4	+2,9

Conclusion: The intake of macronutrients by the subjects does not meet the standard requirements. This situation negatively affects the mastery of subjects and their health. To prevent this, students need to adhere to a healthy lifestyle, abandon harmful habits, and have appropriate understanding of the culture of nutrition.

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